

STRUCTURE AND INFLUENCE OF THE MEDIA FIELD

Xabibullayeva Ruxsora Dilshod qizi

Student of Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

ruxsoraxabibullayeva85@gmail.com

Abstract: This article presents the facts that the global changes taking place in the environment surrounding print media have a significant impact on their character and changes in the economic, political, and technological layers of society.

Key words: internet network, facebook, twitter, odnoklassniki, global network, email mail, social network.

At the current stage of world development, the process of globalization is entering all spheres of society's life. In particular, in the field of information, it is clearly manifested and is going on in an integral way. The information sector is considered as a strategic resource of development. The global informatization of the society forms the core of scientific-technical, economic and social development and is becoming the main factor of development.

Today, the global changes taking place in the environment surrounding print media have a significant impact on their character. This is primarily related to changes in the economic, political, and technological layers of society.

In terms of the number of users on the Internet, the social network Facebook is currently leading with 500,000,000 users. It is followed by MySpace (255,000,000 users), Twitter (200,000,000 users), Windows Live Spaces (120,000,000 users), Habbo Hotel (120,000,000 users), V Kontakte (110,000,000 users), Friendster (90,000,000 users), Hi5(80,000,000 users), Tagged.com (70,000,000). Goals and objectives of Odnoklassniki (odnoklasniki.ru) social network. On such websites, you usually post information about yourself (birthday, school, hobbies, etc.). In turn, you can get this type of information about the participant you are looking for. The triumphant march of social networks on the Internet began in 1995 with the creation of the American social network Classmate.com (Odnoklassniki is considered its Russian analogue). The purpose of this social network is to search, find and communicate with classmates through the Internet. Their tasks are to create networks of mutual interest and maintain communication. Of course, the main purpose of creating these web pages is to make money on the one hand, and on the other hand, to popularize the page and to form groups of people with the same worldview. The downside is that you can't control the groups that are formed.

Purposes and tasks of Classmate (classmate.uz) social network. This website has the same goals and objectives as the creation of Odnoklassniki (odnoklasniki.ru) social

network, it was created and adapted only for citizens of Uzbekistan.

Goals and objectives of Facebook (facebook.com) social network. In 2004, Harvard University student Mark Zuckerberg managed to launch the famous Facebook site. At first, Facebook was planned to be a messaging site for students. But in just 1 month, more than 200,000 people visited this site. After that, Mark realized that the future of the site was bright, and he began to popularize it. At the same time, more than 2 billion people have registered on the site, and it is the site with the most users in the world. are identical in function and are designed and adapted for English speakers only. In addition, those interested may also check out the following web pages: Last.fm, Linjedln, MySpace. The goals and objectives of their creation are similar to those of the above-mentioned web pages. The culture of using information, including personal information, in social networks.

If you pay attention and analyze the given web pages, you will find the following negative situations and shortcomings:

1. Some users do not register with their names;
2. They set inappropriate photo speeds;
3. They are disrespectful in mutual communication;
4. They write nonsense, sometimes use wrong information;
5. Despite the fact that the pages are social, they establish political dialogues and so on.

Therefore, the culture of using information, including personal information, in Social Networks means avoiding the above-mentioned negative situations and shortcomings. It should not be forgotten that the information posted by a certain person on the Internet system can be used by other persons or social groups for various purposes. Including, it can be contrary to spirituality and enlightenment. When using social networks, it is necessary to admit that the information there is correct, that they are not deceiving you, and then come to a certain decision.

Internet concept. The Internet is a global computer network operating on the basis of a single standard. Its name has two different interpretations, namely "International Network" and "Interconnected networks". It is an information system that connects local (local) computer networks and consists of a virtual collection with its own separate information space. The Internet network allows all computers connected to it to exchange information. Each client of the Internet network can transmit information to another city or country through his personal computer. For example, looking through the catalog of the Library of Congress in Washington, getting acquainted with the pictures displayed in the last exhibition of the Metropolitan

Museum in New York, participating in international conferences, carrying out bank transactions and even playing chess with Internet clients living in other countries. can be played. Global network concept. The main cells (parts) of the Internet are personal computers and local networks connecting them. The Internet is a representative of the global network. The Internet allows not only to establish communication between individual computers, but also to connect a group of computers. If any local network is directly connected to the Internet, then every workstation (computer) of this network can use Internet services. There are also computers that are independently connected to the Internet, and they are called host computers.

Each computer connected to the network has its own address and can communicate with any user anywhere in the world using it. The Internet allows not only to establish communication between individual computers, but also to connect a group of computers. If any local network is directly connected to the Internet, then every workstation (computer) of this network can use Internet services. There are also computers that are independently connected to the Internet, and they are called host computers.

Each computer connected to the network has its own address and can communicate with any user anywhere in the world using it. Internet and WWW are not the same thing. The Internet defines the collection of computer networks around the world and provides various computer services. These are E-mail, Usenet teleconferencing, FTP file transfer system, Telenet remote terminal access system, Gopher system and World Wide Web - WWW. So the WWW is only a part of the Internet. But it is developing very fast. WWW is a popular type of Internet service. A modem with a computer is enough to connect to it. Therefore, the World Wide Web will become a global information store-library, and it will spread around the world. On the WWW, information is placed on pages. The number of WWW pages has exceeded one hundred million in the last 3 years. Who owns these pages? They are large corporations or small businesses, universities and schools, organizations, magazines and newspapers, or ordinary individuals. These pages contain a variety of information. Today, the WWW is the most convenient way to get and spread information. It allows all computers connected to it to exchange information.

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